

INITIAL TRAINING OF YOUNG ATHLETES IN THE CONDITIONS OF A SPORT CLASS

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Annotation: The article discusses the ways of initial training of athletes in a sports class. The goals and objectives for the formation of sports classes and their effectiveness in the initial training of young athletes are displayed.

Key words: sports class, youth sports school, young athletes, training sessions.

Introduction. The system of training of sports reserves combines various forms of organization of the training process: sports sections of general education schools, children's and youth sports schools, children's and youth clubs, special classes of a sports profile in sports, schools of the Olympic reserve, schools of higher sportsmanship [1, 2, 3]. In this structure, again, an increasing place was given to sports classes. The experience of previous years has shown the advantage of sports classes, which is expressed in increasing the efficiency of general and special physical training, educational work on personality formation and the educational process [4, 5, 6].

The author argues that such classes in secondary schools become an example of discipline, academic performance, efficiency, social work [7, 8]. This very form of study and sports is welcomed by children, instills in them collectivism, and is supported by parents and teachers. It is also noted that pupils of specialized classes of a sports profile show an improvement in morphological and physiological parameters, a decrease in the number of diseases and a higher academic performance relative to the average score.

Specialized classes of a sports profile with an extended day of study are a specific form of work and are created in secondary schools from among the most promising students in terms of sports in conjunction with the Youth Sports School in order to:

- providing conditions for a rational combination of study with an in-depth educational and training process in a sports school;
- implementation of the training of comprehensively developed, highly qualified athletes, mainly in Olympic sports.

The pedagogical process in such classes makes it possible to combine the efforts of physical education teachers and coaches, they have the opportunity to establish a single daily routine for all students, switch to two workouts a day, and organize proper nutrition. Constantly monitor progress and, in contact with teachers in

subjects and parents, conduct a training, educational and educational process [9, 10, 11].

The organization of such classes does not require additional costs, since their activities are carried out within the limits of the appropriations established for extended-day groups in a general education school.

In track and field athletics, on the basis of the position, specialized classes of a sports profile are created, starting from the sixth grade, after the children have completed two years of initial sports training. Preliminary and initial basic training often takes place without taking into account the requirements of future specialization. However, the peculiarities of the children's organism allow starting the initial sports training in running, jumping and throwing from the age of 10 years [12, 13, 14].

It should be borne in mind that the initial athletics training is the base for many sports. Positive results of practical experience show that it is possible to start such training in the conditions of sports classes already from the fourth grade [15, 16]. This will allow young athletes to undergo targeted training for two years according to unified programs, taking into account the requirements of the proposed future specialization, as well as to implement a differentiated approach in the educational, training and educational process, taking into account the individual predisposition and readiness of children. Therefore, this form of work with young athletes can be recognized as very promising [17, 18].

To date, the tasks of the stage of initial sports specialization in athletics can be most successfully solved in the conditions of sports classes when combining the capabilities of children's and youth sports schools and general education schools without additional financial costs. Approbation of this situation in the course of a two-year experiment suggests that the construction and functioning of the pedagogical system for the selection of young athletes and their orientation towards targeted training in sprinting should be carried out from the age of ten in a sports class, providing for the following organizational and methodological measures:

- preview and control-pedagogical testing of third-grade students;
- recruitment of preparatory groups of general physical training from among the best children and conducting game-oriented classes with them in the last quarter of the academic year;
- holding control competitions and distribution of young athletes into training groups or organizing a specialized class of a sports profile in athletics.

Training programs may consist of a set of specially designed training tasks, taking into account the intended specialization. In order to expand the range of influence on the body, these tasks should be structured in such a way that they allow varying the pace and intensity of performance, the amplitude of movements, and complicating the starting positions in adjacent attempts of individual exercises. Up to 30% of training tasks are game-oriented.

In the general structure of the content composition, funds can be allocated aimed at the primary solution of the problems of general physical education in the amount of up to 30%, multi-specialized training in the amount of up to 60% and special training up to 10% of the total time of training sessions. In turn, in the structure of multi-specialized and special training, the following ratio of funds aimed at the development of physical qualities was taken: up to 35% - the education of speed-strength qualities, 25% for the education of speed, up to 20% for the education of strength, 10% for the education speed endurance and 10% for the development of special flexibility. In general, a rather pronounced effect was achieved in the education of all the physical qualities necessary for athletes and the formation of the necessary motor skills.

Conclusions. It can be assumed that the initial specialized training and orientation of children to the future narrow specialization in athletics can be carried out with great success if classes begin in the conditions of sports classes no later than 10 years old. It should be noted that the conditions for the activity of such classes make it possible to unite the efforts of coaches, school teachers, parents and the team of children with the greatest effect in the general system of training sports reserves. They consistently and in a complex can solve all the tasks of the stage of initial sports specialization, the tasks of guiding children and their selection to continue playing sports in the next link - training groups with in-depth specialization.

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